

ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation: *The article is devoted to the analysis of the problem of ecological education of children in preschool educational institutions and scientific and technological research to solve it. Problems of ecological education in preschool. On the basis of the experimental data of the preschool educational institution, the preparatory group studied experimental methods of ecological education of children.*

Keywords. *preschool education, preschool children, ecological education, ecological culture, analytical materials, excursions, practical exercises.*

Аннотация: *Статья посвящена анализу проблемы экологического воспитания детей в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях и научно-техническим исследованиям по ее решению. Проблемы экологического воспитания в дошкольном возрасте. На основе экспериментальных данных дошкольного образовательного учреждения в подготовительной группе изучались экспериментальные методы экологического воспитания детей.*

Ключевые слова: *дошкольное образование, дошкольники, экологическое воспитание, экологическая культура, аналитические материалы, экскурсии, практические занятия.*

An effective solution to the problem of forming the ecological culture of the population is possible only in the implementation of continuous environmental education, the first stage of which is pre-school education (in the family, in PED). This stage should be considered the most important, because at this age she child is formed the basic moral principles of attitude to nature.

Environmental education in PED includes the formation of children's conscious attitude to nature, the development of the Simplest practical skills of interaction with it, as well as the development of environmental awareness, ecological culture of those involved in the upbringing of preschool children.

At the stage of pre-school education, ecological education is based on the important role in the formation of personality, at this age is lays the foundation for children's interaction with nature, begins to arouse interest in social life, including their bodies The experience of PED in the field of the studied problem was analyzed. The main purpose of the analysis is to find the most effective ways to shape the value of preschool children in the environment. A positive basis for the ecological upbringing of children is that they are aware of the reality around them.

The analysis of the work experience to teachers who come to the refresher course allows us to conclude that the search for optimal ways of environmental education is always carried out by teachers. At the same time different visual aids, different forms of educational work, teaching form of different methods and techniques. However, the results of the survey of 92 teachers of PEDs show the weakness of the methodological readiness of teachers for the effective implementation of the tasks of environmental education of children. Almost all educators said that they would introduce children to environmental facts ant examples, mainly from children's literature, which is very lacking in special biological or ecological literature.

At the same time, most educators carry out environmental education in and out of kindergarten, in the wild, in classrooms, during the months and during walks, without direct acquaintance with the natural ecological phenomena which cannot be considered positive. Educators of ten assess children's positive attitudes to ware nature based on the information they are able to convey and very little on their be how oral and practical.

Wet basic environmental consepts do you introduce your children to in the preschool curriculum?

More than 80 % of the audience could not give a clear answer. More than 20 % are wild and domestic animals, 23 % talked about the importance of animals and plants in human life 26 % talked about nature.

The role of main nature (12.3%), the impacts of the environment on human health (19.0%) Responses were received such as the aesthetic value of the beauty of animate and inanimate nature (7.2%). The answers to the above questions show that educators do not pay much attention to aesthetics, Forms and methods of education are not fully implemented, which shows that future preschool teachers are not sufficiently prepared.

There are a number of shortcomings in environmental education in PED practice the content of environmental education is not clearly defined. As a result of the analysis of the author's programs of ecological education developed for PEDs, we have identified tasks with PEDs teachers:

- formation of ecologically relevant themes and tasks for certain groups;
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- Tariffs for the leading and inter related environmental concepts of each product

and the choice of materials on which to strengthen them;

- Identify methods and forms appropriate to the content of the lesson;
- Selection of teaching aids necessary for the formation of environmental perceptions;

Methods and forms of training include:

- organization of observation of living objects of ecological environment;
- creation of problematic situations, including environmental material;
- Selection of the object of the excursion, determination of the theme and route of

excursions of ecological content;

- Conducting environmental games, etc.

Various environmental sources are widely used in the product, The children

learned poems, listened to music about nature, and drew natural objects and landscapes.

Most of the activities are aimed at introducing children. Most of the activities are aimed at introducing children to the creatures of the earth, because children are especially close to the world of adolescents and animals. For example, the training group “Flowers around us”. In preparation for it, a stand with illustrations of plants discussed in the course was developed, a musical accompaniment and slides with images of various flowering plants were selected.

The lesson is “a wonderful world of flowers” (flowers decorate the earth, surround us everywhere,) give us joy: When flowers disappear, it is hard to imagine how much nature loses its charm when the diversity of colors and flavors dwindles; many flowers come to us from different countries, they are a decoration of our land, ornament of our lives.

The teacher then talked about the time of flowering of different flowers (forexample: tulips, violets, roses, carnations.) in their natural conditions and in green houses, showing illustrations and slides, riddles about plants were widely used (“The roof rises without taking its feet of the ground, the trumpets vibrate to every position trumpet”), etc. The content of the lesson includes questions about the relationship of ecological plants with the environment. When do tulips and roses bloom in nature? Why is the wild rose bush called “shipovnik?” what is the importance of thorns in the life of this plant? What is the importance onions for Lola, some activities are held in the corner of nature. Thus, PED children are a variety of plants (monster, tradessantia, aloe, house grapes, etc.) from distant hands for example, it was explained why monster grows in forests why it is called weeping and how the ability to get rid of excess water is related to its living conditions. The educator told the children about the well-known aloe as a desert plant adapted to retain moisture in its leaves and demonstrated their succulent flash. During the training educators demonstrated simple experiment’s, such as determining the movement of plants displayed in the window. The children gradually observed the

leaves of these plants looking at the light and come to the conclusion that light is necessary for plants.

The content of some group sessions will be entirely ecological. In the preparatory group, “What is ecology?” training on the topic was conducted in the first lesson children were introduced to the methods of ecology in a convenient way, explaining the importance of science for the proper management and organization of ecological of “habitat” and environmental factors were discussed during the lesson. Despite the complexity of the materials, the lesson was fun for 6 years-olds.

A training on “Environmental Alphabet” was organized in the formation of primary environmental literacy. In it, children were introduced to the basic rules of behavior in nature. During the lesson, the following questions were discussed: Why can tree branches be broken? Why is it impossible to light a fire? What to do with the leftovers after eating in the bosom of nature?

The diversity of the topic of the group training, organized by several groups, the possibility of making changes to the educational program in different PED. The general features of all the lessons on various topics, the ecological orientation of the material, the desire of teachers to involve children in active activities during the preparation and conduct of the lesson are achieved in the following ways:

- fun, emotional, colourful materials for children were selected;
- frequent use of live plants and animals during training: the children’s interest was aroused;
- changes in training techniques (story, interview, demonstration);
- the emotional state of children is positively influenced by the design of the premises and the music.

Especially due to the age characteristics of the children, to gather they participated in the “creation” of “ecological” fairy tales, theatrical performances, children’s performances, memorized role. In addition to group activities, teachers conducted trips in collaboration with teachers who visited the field trip, in preparation for it, paid special attention to the selection of excursion sites, the

development of age appropriate tasks. Through research, children gained a clear idea of the objects. For example, during excursions dedicated to winter events in nature the following issues were discussed: when did winter come to our country? What signs do we know and animals adapt to winter? The material of the excursions was later used in group activities. During the excursion, the development of children's cognitive processes, the formation of basic travel skills, children's recreation, exercise, etc.

An analysis of the materials of our study shows that the pupils of the experimental groups of preschools, where we worked on the proposed system were generally interested in environmental issues and nature protection, and knew the basic rules of behavior in nature. It is also important to organize such excursions as often as possible, taking into account the interests of children.

Thus, the results of the pedagogical experiment, which was reflected in the positive feedback from parents and educators of preschool education, in raising the environmental awareness of quantity and quality, Said that concluded.

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